

Behaviour of Halogenated Nitrobenzenes with β -Diketones. Part IV Halogeno-nitro Derivatives of Acetylacetone and Their Cyclisation to Anthranils

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Dinitrophenyldiacetylmethanes have been prepared by the interaction of halogeno-dinitrobenzenes and acetylacetone. The β -ketones, obtained from them on hydrolysis, have been cyclised to halogeno-nitroanthranils.

The monosodio derivative of acetylacetone reacts with 1-chloro-2,4-dinitrobenzene to form 2,4-dinitrophenyldiacetylmethane¹. This on heating with moderately concentrated sulphuric acid is hydrolysed to 2,4-dinitrophenylacetone and with concentrated sulphuric acid, it is cyclised to 6-nitroanthranil².

During the present work 2-chloro-, 2-bromo-, and 2-iodo-4,6-dinitrophenyldiacetylmethanes have been prepared by the interaction of the sodio derivative of acetylacetone and 1,2-dichloro-, 1-chloro-2-bromo-, or 1-chloro-2-iodo-4,6-dinitrobenzene respectively. The behaviour of these substituted dinitrophenyldiacetylmethanes (I) is not quite normal; these fail to react with hydrazine hydrate, phenylhydrazine, semicarbazide, and hydroxylamine, apparently due to presence of 2,6-disubstituted dinitrophenyl group in them. Like β -diketones these are, however, hydrolysed to monoketones (II). The latter, when heated with concentrated sulphuric acid, yield the corresponding nitroanthranils (III).

Like 6-nitroanthranil², these halogeno-nitroanthranils (III) form in ethanolic solution salts with hydrazine hydrate and molecular compounds with mercuric chloride. On heating with sodium carbonate solution, these are hydrolysed to nitroanthranilic acids (IV) and are oxidised with potassium dichromate and sulphuric acid to dicarboxydinitro-azoxybenzenes (V). They form nitroacetanthranils (nitromethylbenzoxazones) (VI) with

1. Joshi and Gambhir, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 78, 2222.
2. *Idem*, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, 26, 3714.

acetic anhydride and zinc acetate, 2-phenylindazoles (VII) with aniline, and bis-indazolyls (VIII) with hydrazine acetate and acetic acid.

[a: X=Cl; b: X=Br; c: X=I]

The 2-phenylindazoles and bis-indazolyls dissolve in concentrated hydrochloric acid and are precipitated from their solutions on dilution or addition of an alkali.

EXPERIMENTAL

(2-Chloro-4,6-dinitrophenyl) diacetylmethane (Ia: X=Cl).—The monosodium derivative of acetylacetone (1 g.) in absolute ethanol (10 ml) and 1,2-dichloro-4,6-dinitrobenzene (2.37 g.) were refluxed for 1 hr. and filtered. The filtrate on keeping deposited crystals, which on recrystallisation from EtOH provided 1.85 g. of (2-chloro-4,6-dinitrophenyl) diacetylmethane as colorless needles, m.p. 108°. (Found: Cl, 11.75. $C_{11}H_9O_6N_2Cl$ requires Cl, 11.81%).

(2-Bromo-4,6-dinitrophenyl) diacetylmethane (Ib: X=Br) was prepared similarly as above by refluxing 1-chloro-2-bromo-4,6-dinitrobenzene (2.8 g.) and the ketone derivative for 2 hr. The filtrate on keeping deposited light brown crystals, which after purification with activated charcoal and recrystallisation from acetic acid afforded 1.79 g. of the product (Ib: X=Br) as colorless needles, m.p. 127°. (Found: Br, 23.23. $C_{11}H_9O_6N_2Br$ requires Br, 23.19%).

(2-Iodo-4,6-dinitrophenyl) diacetylmethane (Ic: X=I) was prepared by the procedure adopted for compound (Ia), using 1-chloro-2-iodo-4,6-dinitrobenzene (4.2 g.) and the ketone derivative. Recrystallisation from ethanol furnished 1.97 g. of the product as pale yellow needles, m.p. 129°. (Found: I, 32.07. $C_{11}H_9O_6N_2I$ requires I, 32.40%).

2-Chloro-4,6-dinitrophenylacetone (IIa: X=Cl) was prepared by heating (Ia: X=Cl) with moderately concentrated sulphuric acid for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. Crystallisation from acetic acid provided 82% of the pure product as colorless crystals, m.p. 99°. (Found: Cl, 13.59. $C_9H_7O_5N_2Cl$ requires Cl, 13.73%).

2-Bromo-4,6-dinitrophenylacetone (IIb; X=Br) was similarly prepared as compound (IIa). Recrystallisation from ethanol afforded 80% of the pure product as buff needles, m.p. 112°. (Found: Br, 26.01. $C_9H_7O_5N_2Br$ requires Br, 26.40%).

2-Iodo-4,6-dinitrophenylacetone (IIc; X=I) was obtained in the same way as the preceding compound (IIa). Recrystallisation from dilute acetic acid provided 77% of the derivative (IIc) as brown needles, m.p. 110°. (Found: I, 35.96. $C_9H_7O_5N_2I$ requires I, 36.28%).

4-Chloro-6-nitroanthranil (IIIa) was prepared by heating (IIa) with H_2SO_4 (conc.) at 105-110° for 3 hr. Recrystallisation from ethanol afforded 50% of the anil (IIIa) as colorless needles, m.p. 134°. (Found: N, 13.88. $C_7H_5O_3N_2Cl$ requires N, 14.10%).

Hydrazine salt of (IIIa) was obtained as yellow needles from ethanol (69%), m.p. 165°. (Found: N, 24.01. $C_7H_7O_3N_4Cl$ requires N, 24.24%).

Mercuric chloride compound of (IIIa) was obtained as lemon-yellow needles from ethanol (68%), m.p. 170°. (Found: Cl, 22.41. $C_7H_5O_3N_2Cl \cdot HgCl_2$ requires Cl, 22.65%).

4-Bromo-6-nitroanthranil (IIIb) was prepared by the procedure adopted for compound (IIIa) by using (IIb). Recrystallisation from acetic acid provided 49% of the anil (IIIb) as yellow prisms, m.p. 125°. (Found: N, 11.41. $C_7H_5O_3N_2Br$ requires N, 11.52%).

4-Iodo-6-nitroanthranil (IIIc) was obtained similarly as compound (IIIa) by using (IIc). Recrystallisation from acetic acid furnished 46% of the anil (IIIc) as pale yellow plates, m.p. 123°. (Found: N, 9.39. $C_7H_5O_3N_2I$ requires N, 9.65%).

2-Amino-6-chloro-4-nitrobenzoic acid (IVa) was prepared by heating (IIIa) with an aqueous solution of sodium carbonate. It was crystallised from acetic acid in orange plates, m.p. 269°, yield 48.6%. (Found: N, 12.83. $C_7H_5O_4N_2Cl$ requires N, 12.93%).

2,2'-Dicarboxy-3,3'-dichloro-5,5'-dinitroazoxybenzene (Va) was obtained by heating (IIIa) with a saturated solution of $K_2Cr_2O_7$ and H_2SO_4 (conc.). It was crystallised from acetic acid in lemon-yellow cubes, m.p. 272°, yield 59%. (Found: N, 12.45; titre value, 227.8. $C_{14}H_6O_9N_4Cl_2$ requires N, 12.58%; titre value, 222.5).

6-Chloro-4-nitroacetanthranil (**5-chloro-7-nitro-2-methylbenzoxazone** (VIa) and **6-chloro-4-nitro-N-acetylanthranilic acid**) were prepared by heating (IIIa) with acetic anhydride and zinc acetate in glacial acetic acid. Recrystallisation from acetic acid afforded 38% of 6-chloro-4-nitroacetanthranil as dirty yellow prisms, m.p. 152°. (Found: C, 44.69; H, 2.02. $C_9H_5O_4N_2Cl$ requires C, 44.90; H, 2.07%).

The mother liquor from the dilute acetic acid provided 51% of 6-chloro-4-nitroacetylanthranilic acid as colorless needles, m.p. 254°. (Found: N, 10.74. $C_9H_7O_5N_2Cl$ requires N, 10.83%).

4-Chloro-6-nitro-2-phenylindazole (VIIa) was obtained by heating (IIIa) with aniline at 140° for 3 hr. Crystallisation from acetic acid afforded 35% of the product (VIIa) as yellow needles, m.p. 311°. (Found: C, 56.45; H, 2.88. $C_{13}H_8O_2N_2Cl$ requires C, 57.04; H, 2.93%).

4,4'-Dichloro-6,6'-dinitro-2,2'-bis-indazolyl (VIIIa) was prepared by heating (IIa) with hydrazine hydrate in glacial acetic acid for 2 hr. Recrystallisation from ethyl acetate provided 66% of the product as red needles, m.p. 250°. (Found: C, 42.39; H, 1.56. $C_{14}H_6O_4N_6Cl_2$ requires C, 42.74; H, 1.53%).

4-Chloro-6-nitro-2-anilinoindazole was obtained by heating (IIIa) with phenylhydrazine for 3 hr. Crystallisation from acetic acid furnished the pure product as reddish brown needles, m.p. 179°, yield 48%. (Found: C, 53.71; H, 3.08. $C_{13}H_9O_2N_4Cl$ requires C, 54.07; H, 3.12%).

TABLE I

Derivatives from 4-bromo-6-nitroanthranil (IIIb).

Derivatives.	M.P.	Colour.	% Yield.	Found.	Reqd.
1 Hydrazine salt	163°	Orange	66.0	N : 24.01%	24.24%
2 Mercuric chloride compound	158°	Colorless	64.0	Cl : 13.60	13.81
3 2-Amino-6-bromo-4-nitrobenzoic acid	278°	Brown	50.1	N : 10.68	10.73
4 2,2'-Dicarboxy-5,5'-dinitro-3,3'-dibromo-azeoxybenzene	292°	Pale yellow	54.0	N : 10.42 *(259.1)	10.48 (267.0)
5 6-Bromo-4-nitroacetoanthranil	180°	Yellow	44.3	C : 37.68 H : 1.62	37.89 1.75
6 6-Bromo-4-nitroacetoanthranilic acid	240°	Colorless	45.8	N : 9.15	9.24
7 4-Bromo-6-nitro-2-phenylindazole	318°	Yellow	36.0	C : 48.70 H : 2.55	49.05 2.51
8 4,4'-Dibromo-6,6'-dinitro-bis-indazolyl	275°	Red	64.0	C : 34.67 H : 1.22	34.85 1.24
9 4-Bromo-6-nitro-2-anilinoindazole	175°	Brown	49.0	C : 46.58 H : 2.77	46.84 2.70

TABLE II

Derivatives from 4-iodo-6-nitroanthranil (IIIc).

Derivatives.	M.P.	Colour.	% Yield.	Found.	Reqd.
1 Hydrazine salt	178°	Red	65	N : 17.11%	17.39%
2 Mercuric chloride compound.	163°	Light brown	59	Cl : 12.72	12.65
3 2-Amino-6-iodo-4-nitrobenzoic acid	271°	Brown	45	N : 8.92	8.90
4 2,2'-Dicarboxy-5,5'-diiodo-3,3'-diiodo-azeoxybenzene	298°	Light brown	50	N : 8.05 *(308)	8.91 (314)
5 6-Iodo-4-nitroacetoanthranil	170°	Pale yellow	34	C : 32.49 H : 1.49	32.53 1.51
6 6-Iodo-4-nitroacetoanthranilic acid	240°	Light brown	52	N : 8.10	8.00
7 4-Iodo-6-nitro-2-phenylindazole	332°	Brown	31	C : 42.41 H : 2.15	42.74 2.19
8 4,4'-Diiodo-6,6'-dinitro-bis-indazolyl	289°	Brown	60	C : 29.00 H : 1.08	29.17 1.04
9 4-Iodo-6-nitro-2-anilinoindazole	180°	Brown	40	C : 40.54 H : 2.39	41.05 2.37

* Figures in parentheses refer to titre values.

The derivatives obtained from 4-bromo-6-nitroanthranil (IIIb) and 4-iodo-6-nitroanthranil (IIIc) by adopting methods similar to those employed in the case of 4-chloro-6-nitroanthranil are shown in Tables I and II respectively.